

Appendix H: Correspondence analysis tables

TABLE 5: Relationship of correspondence between GOVERN and IDENTIFY functions

Relationship	Govern coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Risk Management Strategy - Improvement	(0.1830, -0.0277)	(0.1265, 0.0233)	1.5804
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management - Asset Management	(-0.2057 , 0.0087)	(-0.2189 , 0.0962)	1.1498
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities - Improvement	(0.1607, 0.0497)	(0.1265, 0.0233)	0.9779
Organizational Context - Asset Management	(-0.0155, 0.0572)	(-0.2189, 0.0962)	0.7540
Oversight - Risk Assessment	(-0.0393, -0.0470)	(-0.0585, -0.0451)	0.6981
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management - Risk Assessment	(-0.2057 , 0.0087)	(-0.0585, -0.0451)	0.6926
Policy - Risk Assessment	(-0.0709, -0.0676)	(-0.0585, -0.0451)	0.6386
Organizational Context - Improvement	(-0.0155, 0.0572)	(0.1265 , 0.0233)	0.1390

TABLE 6: Relationship of correspondence between GOVERN and PROTECT functions

Relationship	Govern coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Protect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities - Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	(0.7317, 0.0874)	(0.9961,- 0.2451)	2,0493
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management - Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	(0.1674, 0.1442)	(0.9961, -0.2451)	1.2340
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management - Awareness and Training	(0.1674, 0.1442)	(0.0701, 0.4478)	1.2111
Oversight - Awareness and Training	(-0.1269 , 0.2063)	(0.0701, 0.4478)	1.0647
Risk Management Strategy – Technology Infrastructure Resilience	(-0.2197, 0.0987)	(-0.0279, -0.0701)	0.9444
Organizational Context - Platform Security	(-0.0381 , -0.2429)	(0.0153, -0.1152)	0.8651
Policy - Data Security	(0.0061, -0.3949)	(-0.2134, -0.0973)	0.7868
Oversight - Platform Security	(-0.1269 , 0.2063)	(0.0153 , -0.1152)	0.6865

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TABLE 7: Relationship of correspondence between GOVERN and RECOVER functions

Relationship	Govern coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Recover coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities Incident Recovery - Plan Execution	(0.6916, 0.0000)	(0.2034, 0.0000)	1.2544
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management - Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.3772, -0.0000)	(-0.4252, 0.0000)	0.8032
Risk Management Strategy – Incident Recovery Plan Execution	(0.1572, -0.0000)	(0.2034, 0.0000)	0.6769
Policy – Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.2245, 0.0000)	(-0.4252, 0.0000)	0.6666
Organizational Context - Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.3772, -0.0000)	(-0.4252, 0.0000)	0.5499
Oversight – Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.0210, -0.0000)	(-0.4252, 0.0000)	0.0566

TABLE 8: Relationship of correspondence between GOVERN and RESPOND functions

Relationship	Govern coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Respond coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities - Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(-0.4383, -0.2173)	(-0.3539, -0.4754)	1.8199
Risk Management Strategy – Incident Mitigation	(0.1967, -0.0007)	(0.2993, -0.0503)	1.4624
Policy - Incident Mitigation	(0.3435, -0.2315)	(0.2993, -0.0503)	1.4537
Oversight - Incident Analysis	(-0.0771, 0.2947)	(-0.2343, 0.1740)	1.1947
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management - Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(-0.2786, -0.1433)	(-0.3539, -0.4754)	0.9203
Oversight - Incident Management	(-0.0771, 0.2947)	(-0.0011, 0.0585)	0.6827
Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management - Incident Analysis	(-0.2786, -0.1433)	(-0.2343, 0.1740)	0.5622
Organizational Context - Incident Analysis	(-0.0503, 0.0542)	(-0.2343, 0.1740)	0.4769

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TABLE 9: Relationship of correspondence between IDENTIFY and PROTECT functions

Relationship	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Protect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Risk Assessment - Platform Security	(-0.1507, 0.0513)	(-0.2349, 0.0764)	1.2990
Asset Management - Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	(0.4438, 0.0608)	(0.4634, 0.0392)	1.2016
Asset Management - Data Security	(0.4438, 0.0608)	(0.2059, 0.0032)	1.0638
Improvement Technology- Infrastructure Resilience	(0.0108, -0.0691)	(-0.0747, -0.0701)	0.5936
Asset Management - Awareness and Training	(0.4438, 0.0608)	(0.1086, 0.0554)	0.5391
Improvement – Data Security	(0.0108, -0.0691)	(0.2059, 0.0032)	0.0393

TABLE 10: Relationship of correspondence between IDENTIFY and RESPOND functions

Relationship	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Respond coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Asset Management Incident – Response Reporting and Communication	(2.7802, 0.0685)	(2.2256, 0.0851)	5.6383
Improvement - Incident Mitigation	(-0.1876, 0.1944)	(-0.2347, 0.2256)	1.7335
Risk Assessment - Incident Management	(-0.0815, -0.1563)	(-0.0224, -0.2084)	1.3318
Risk Assessment - Incident Analysis	(-0.0815, -0.1563)	(-0.2130, -0.0255)	0.3785
Improvement - Incident Analysis	(-0.1876, 0.1944)	(-0.2130, -0.0255)	0.2137

TABLE 11: Relationship of correspondence between IDENTIFY and RECOVER functions

Relationship	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Recover coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Improvement – Incident Recovery Plan Execution	(0.1083, -0.0000)	(0.0816, -0.0000)	0.3892
Asset Management - Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.1443, -0.0000)	(-0.1088, -0.0000)	0.3208
Risk Assessment - Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.0321, -0.0000)	(-0.1088, -0.0000)	0.1273

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TABLE 12: Relationship of correspondence between DETECT and GOVERN functions

Relationship	Detect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Govern coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Adverse Event Analysis - Cybersecurity Supply Chain Risk Management	(0.6960, 0.0000)	(0.6134, -0.0000)	2.6651
Continuous Monitoring - Oversight	(-0.3202, 0.0000)	(-0.5245, 0.0000)	2.1828
Adverse Event Analysis -Risk Management Strategy	(0.6960, 0.0000)	(0.2443, 0.0000)	1.6467
Continuous Monitoring - Policy	(-0.3202, 0.0000)	(-0.6782, 0.0000)	1.5713
Continuous Monitoring - Organizational Context	(-0.3202, 0.0000)	(-0.6782, 0.0000)	1.3952
Continuous Monitoring - Roles, Responsibilities, and Authorities	(-0.3202, 0.0000)	(-0.3707, 0.0000)	1.0315

TABLE 13: Relationship of correspondence between DETECT and IDENTIFY functions

Relationship	Detect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Adverse Event Analysis - Risk Assessment	(0.4633, 0.0000)	(0.4175, 0.0000)	2.6811
Continuous Monitoring - Improvement	(-0.3138, 0.0000)	(-0.2672, 0.0000)	1.6502
Continuous Monitoring - Asset Management	(-0.3138, 0.0000)	(-0.5319, 0.0000)	1.5128

TABLE 14: Relationship of correspondence between DETECT and PROTECT functions

Relationship	Detect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Adverse Event Analysis - Awareness and Training	(0.9369, 0.0000)	(0.9221, -0.0000)	8.6563
Continuous Monitoring - Platform Security	(-0.3904, 0.0000)	(-0.4587, 0.0000)	3.5442
Continuous Monitoring - Data Security	(-0.3904, 0.0000)	(-0.4061, -0.0000)	3.4748
Continuous Monitoring – Technology Infrastructure Resilience	(-0.3904, 0.0000)	(-0.3443, -0.0000)	2.8032
Adverse Event Analysis - Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control	(0.9369, 0.0000)	(0.6713, -0.0000)	1.5184

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TABLE 15: Relationship of correspondence between DETECT and RESPOND functions

Relationship	Detect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Continuous Monitoring - Incident Analysis	(-0.0364, 0.0000)	(-0.0714, 0.0000)	0.7153
Adverse Event Analysis - Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(0.1174, 0.0000)	(0.1351, -0.0000)	0.5874
Adverse Event Analysis - Incident Management	(0.1174, 0.0000)	(0.0438, 0.0000)	0.3537
Adverse Event Analysis - Incident Mitigation	(0.1174, 0.0000)	(0.0033, -0.0000)	0.0248
Continuous Monitoring - Incident Mitigation	(-0.0364, 0.0000)	(0.0033, -0.0000)	-0.0248
Continuous Monitoring - Incident Management	(-0.0364, 0.0000)	(0.0438, 0.0000)	-0.3537
Continuous Monitoring - Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(-0.0364, 0.0000)	(0.1351, -0.0000)	-0.5874
Adverse Event Analysis - Incident Analysis	(0.1174, 0.0000)	(-0.0714, 0.0000)	-0.7153

TABLE16: Relationship of correspondence between PROTECT and RECOVER functions

Relationship	Detect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Data Security – Incident Recovery Communication	(0.7071, -0.0000)	(1.0690, 0.0000)	1.3416
Technology Infrastructure Resilience - Incident Recovery Plan Execution	(-0.3536, 0.0000)	(-0.1336, 0.0000)	0.8018
Awareness and Training - Incident Recovery Plan Execution	(-0.3536, -0.0000)	(-0.1336, 0.0000)	0.5303
Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control Incident Recovery Plan Execution	(-0.3536, 0.0000)	(-0.1336, 0.0000)	0.5303
Platform Security - Incident Recovery Communication	(0.1010, -0.0000)	(1.0690, 0.0000)	0.3419
Platform Security - Incident Recovery Plan Execution	(0.1010, -0.0000)	(-0.1336, 0.0000)	-0.3419
Awareness and Training - Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.3536, -0.0000)	(1.0690, 0.0000)	-0.5303
Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control Incident Recovery Communication	(-0.3536, 0.0000)	(1.0690, 0.0000)	-0.5303

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TABLE 17: Relationship of correspondence between PROTECT and RESPOND functions

Relationship	Detect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Awareness and Training - Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(-0.5090, 0.0635)	(-0.7508, 0.1262)	2.6356
Platform Security - Incident Mitigation	(0.0830, 0.1414)	(0.0897, 0.1076)	1.7442
Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control - Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(-0.7465, -0.0686)	(-0.7508, 0.1262)	1.5550
Data Security - Incident Analysis	(0.0165, -0.0882)	(-0.0383, -0.1278)	1.2666
Technology Infrastructure Resilience - Incident Management	(0.0726, -0.0651)	(0.0643, -0.0128)	1.0752
Identity Management, Authentication, and Access Control Incident Analysis	(-0.7465, -0.0686)	(-0.0383, -0.1278)	0.3981
Technology Infrastructure Resilience - Incident Analysis	(0.0726, -0.0651)	(-0.0383, -0.1278)	0.1185
Awareness and Training - Incident Analysis	(-0.5090, 0.0635)	(-0.0383, -0.1278)	0.0251

TABLE 18: Relationship of correspondence between RECOVER and RESPOND functions

Relationship	Detect coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Identify coordinates (Dim , Dim2)	Adjusted Pearson Residual
Incident Recovery Communication - Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(3.2404, 0.0000)	(2.2386, -0.0000)	3.3132
Incident Recovery Plan Execution – Incident Mitigation	(-0.1473, 0.0000)	(-0.2132, -0.0000)	0.9789
Incident Recovery Plan Execution – Incident Management	(-0.1473, 0.0000)	(-0.2132, 0.0000)	0.6763
Incident Recovery Plan Execution – Incident Analysis	(-0.1473, 0.0000)	(-0.2132, -0.0000)	0.3960
Incident Recovery Communication - Incident Analysis	(3.2404, 0.0000)	(-0.2132, -0.0000)	-0.3960
Incident Recovery Communication - Incident Management	(3.2404, 0.0000)	(-0.2132, 0.0000)	-0.6763
Incident Recovery Communication - Incident Mitigation	(3.2404, 0.0000)	(-0.2132, -0.0000)	-0.9789
Incident Recovery Plan Execution – Incident Response Reporting and Communication	(-0.1473, 0.0000)	(2.2386, -0.0000)	-3.3132